

REFORMING THE INDEPENDENT SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article reviews the laws and decisions on integrated education in the global education system and the reforms aimed at its implementation in Uzbekistan, as well as specialization of school education, continuing professional education and determination of quality standards of higher education

It is no coincidence that the 19th century is called the "age of technology". Rapid development, our social way of life requires the development of science and technology, more innovative facilities. Naturally, at the same time, the period requires society, especially young people, to be aware not only of changes in technical, automatic, symbolic, mobile, linguistic, Internet, computer technology, but also to be their creator. It is gratifying that all the conditions have been created for the region, the republic, the region, the world to demonstrate our talent and intellectual potential.

After independence, as in all spheres, great changes have taken place in the field of education. In particular, it is no exaggeration to say that the laws, decisions and reforms aimed at the implementation of the teaching process and assessment criteria, organized on the basis of integrative principles in the world education system, have become a turning point in the education system of Uzbekistan. So far, there has been integration in laws and regulations aimed at improving education, some of which we consider appropriate:

1. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" was adopted by the

Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 19, 2020, and approved by the Senate on August 7, 2020. Date of entry into force: 24.09.2020. The law, adopted by the world's leading countries, focuses on such aspects as the integrated approach to the education system and the teachings of great ancestors. We see this in Article 10 of the Law:

“Article 10. Vocational education

Vocational education includes the following levels of occupation and specialization:

primary vocational education;
secondary vocational education;
secondary special vocational education.

Main part.

Primary vocational education in vocational schools is provided on a free basis on the basis of graduates of the ninth grade on the basis of two-year integrated programs of general education and special subjects in the form of full-time education.

Secondary vocational education in colleges on the basis of a state order or fee-for-service, depending on the complexity of professions and specialties, general secondary, full-time, part-time and part-time education for up to two years. rta is based on special education as well as primary vocational education.

Due to the complexity of professions and specialties on the basis of state order or fee-based contract on the basis of general secondary, secondary special, primary professional and secondary vocational education in secondary special vocational technical schools, the duration full-time, part-time and part-time forms of education for at least two years. Prior to the enactment of this Law, citizens who received secondary special, vocational

education (nine years of general secondary and three years of secondary special, vocational education) also received secondary professional and vocational education. rta is entitled to special professional training. Vocational schools, colleges and technical schools ensure that students have the career and specialization of their choice. Citizens have the right to a second and subsequent vocational training on a contract basis. ” Thus, from the day the law officially came into force, the focus on integrated education in the education system will increase [1].

The indisputable need for INTEGRATIVE education, reflected in the teachings of the East and the West, tried to establish by the Jadids, proved to have positive results in the educational process, education in Uzbekistan We will see more clearly below that many steps have been taken on the importance of reforms. Including,

- Order of the Minister of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [2]. (Registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 3, 2018, registration number 3032) This curriculum is based on international best practices and the experience of South Korea. The program provides an individual approach to each child, and integrative views are reflected in the following sentences of the program:

Principles of organization of educational process in MTC:

- taking into account the rights of the child, the specific features and potential of development;

- Interdependence of all types of development in the educational process;
 - protection and strengthening of the child's health, meeting his needs, including his mobility needs;
 - support the child's creative abilities;
 - education and development through play;
 - creating a favorable environment for the development and social adaptation of the child;
 - providing a safe environment for the child;
 - Cooperation of MTC with family, community and school;
 - increase the value of national cultural traditions and respect for the culture of other nations, taking into account the peculiarities of the culture of other nations;
- [3] "

Attracting students to the lesson. For this purpose, the following law was adopted:

- Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the education system in the field of information technology, development of research and their integration with the dog industry" Improving the system of training in the field of information technology "Digital Uzbekistan - One of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the strategy "2030", the development of digital technologies and ensuring their widespread introduction into everyday life. Entered into force on 07.10.2020, the following views on integration are reflected:
"3. The main directions of the activities of specialized schools are: to create conditions for the creative development of students, including the integration of the project "One Million Programmers" into

school curricula, to teach students the basics of information technology and computer programming to organize training;"

"... Ensure the gradual integration of the subject of" Computer Science and Information Technology "in specialized and other secondary schools with the curriculum of the" One Million Programmers "project;"

"Integrate science with the teaching process and take steps to increase teachers' interest in the learning process."

The organization of all disciplines in integration with information technology, established by law, is a guarantee of effective organization of the education system. One of the next major reforms in Uzbek education is the creation of the Presidential School in accordance with international standards. - The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Regulations on the Presidential Schools" came into force on 26.06.2019. goals and objectives include:

"The purpose of establishing presidential schools is to identify gifted children, create an integrated system of teaching and educating them using advanced technologies in the educational process, further support and encouragement of talented youth. to form a spiritually mature and intellectually harmonious generation."

The main tasks of the Presidential schools are:

- identify, select and educate gifted children, create conditions for their full development, as well as reveal the intellectual, scientific and creative potential of students;

- in-depth study of natural and exact sciences, organization of mastering foreign languages, engineering and information technologies, creating the necessary conditions for the development of innovative ideas and developments of students;

The uniqueness of this school is that it selects talented students on the basis of STEAM. As for the term STEAM, the following information is available on the Internet: If we expand this abbreviation, we get: STEAM is S - science, T - technology, E - engineering, A - art and M - math. In English, it's science, technology, engineering, art, and math. These routes are becoming the most popular in the modern world. That is why today the STEAM system is evolving as one of the main trends. STEAM is based on the direction of education and the application of a practical approach, as well as the integration of all five areas into a single education system [3].

In the resolution we find the following sentences:

Among the graduates of the fourth (first - fourth - ninth) grades of secondary schools of the Republic to the Presidential schools are gifted and talented STEAM subjects (mathematics, biology (natural sciences), computer science and information on the basis of grades) technologies, physics, algebra, geometry, chemistry) on a competitive basis.

Another change in the field of education in our country is the introduction of the

International Assessment System, which consists of the interdependence of disciplines. In particular,

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2018 No 997 "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system" The National Center for International Research on Quality Assessment in Education was established under the State Inspectorate for Quality Control in Education [5].

- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the Concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PIP-5712. The quality of education aimed at assessing the level of literacy of students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences on the basis of achieving membership in the top 30 countries and the organization of international research in the field of quality assessment in public education tasks to create a national system of evaluation are defined.

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in public education". This resolution came into force on 10.12.2018 and Attempts are being made to find it. The following figure provides a brief overview of international evaluation programs.

PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) - an international program for assessing student achievement;

PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) - an international comparative study of student performance in reading literacy at the fourth grade;

TIMMS ((Test, Measurement, and Diagnostic Equipment) Integrated Maintenance Management System) - an international monitoring that studies the quality of mathematics and science in school;

ICILS (International Computer and Information Literacy Study) - The study measures international differences in students' computer and information literacy.

Conclusion.

To sum up, the resolution states the following about the use of international testing practices:

a) to organize international research (hereinafter referred to as international research) on the following international evaluation programs:

Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS) - to assess the level of reading and comprehension of text in primary school students;

Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) - to assess the level of mastery of 4th and 8th grade students in mathematics and science;

The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) - to assess the literacy of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and science;

The Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) - to study the teaching and learning environment in general secondary education and the working conditions of teachers in general secondary education [5];

Tests like these help to develop students' intelligence. If we consider the Pisa test,

which is based on integration alone, this type of test is especially important because it is organized in an interdisciplinary way. It is a program that assesses the literacy of 15-year-old students in different countries (reading, mathematics, science) and their ability to apply knowledge in practice. Monitoring the quality of students' knowledge in "Pisa" is defined in 5 areas: reading literacy, mathematical literacy, computer literacy, financial literacy, natural science literacy. In 2021, Uzbekistan is expected to participate in 3 areas (reading literacy, mathematical literacy, natural science literacy).

It is relevant to say that since independence, Uzbekistan's education system has undergone unprecedented changes: on the basis of an integrated approach, on the basis of international tests. All the reforms carried out in the field of laws and decisions aimed at improving the process and quality of education will undoubtedly be the basis for the birth of Abu Ali ibn Sina, Khorezmi and Ulugbek, Alisher and Babur in the future.

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